

CHEMISTRY

CF₃-β-DIKETONES AND TRIMETHYLHALOSILANES AS SYNTHONS FOR TETRAHYDROPYRIMIDINES

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Abstract

Trimethylchlorosilane, which is an effective promoter and water-condensing agent, was used for the first time in cyclocondensation reactions with substituted ureas and thioureas. By varying the solvent, ratio of reagents, temperature and reaction time, 100% conversion was achieved for the model compounds. The optimal conditions for the reaction were: reaction temperature 20°C, dimethylformamide solvent, reaction time 48 hours, presence of 4 equivalents of Me₃SiCl. The use of Me₃SiCl made it possible to introduce a wide range of aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes, mono- and disubstituted ureas and thioureas into the reaction.

CF₃-β-diketones were used for the first time in cyclocondensation reactions as bifunctional reagents. The DMF/TMSCl system was used.

Keywords: CF₃-β-diketones, trimethylhalosilanes, benzaldehyde, acetoethyl acetate, phenylurea, phenylthiourea.

Introduction.

At the end of the 19th century, the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones of the general formula (1) was carried out by the method of condensation of aromatic aldehyde, urea and acetoacetic ester [1].

This reaction is currently undergoing a new stage of development. It was found that 6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine ethyl carboxylate is formed during the condensation of acetoacetic ester with urea and benzaldehyde. An identical product can be obtained: a) by the interaction of benzaldehyde with β-carbamidocrotonic ester, b) by the reaction of benzylidene diureide with acetoacetic ester, c) by condensation of α-benzalacetoacetate with urea. These counter-syntheses unambiguously proved the structure of 6-methyl-4-phenyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine ethyl carboxylate. The next article devoted to this cyclocondensation was published only in 1929 [2]. In the early 1930s, attention was paid to this reaction by Folkes, Hartwood, and Johnson [3]. They proposed a modified method of its implementation, thanks to

which it was possible to expand the range of reagents and increase product yields.

In the following years, until the end of the 30s, only about a dozen publications on this topic were published. With the development of pharmaceutical chemistry, interest in tetrahydropyrimidine derivatives began to grow. Reviews were published [4-6]. The number of articles since the beginning of the 70s has reached over a hundred.

The fact that the reaction is three-component makes it possible to vary the structure of its products. So as a methylene carbonyl component derivatives of β-ketocarboxylic acids, β-diketones, α-nitro-, α-aryl- and some α-heteryl ketones and aldehydes were used. Aldehydes are aromatic and heteroaromatic, some aliphatic. Substituted and unsubstituted ureas, thioureas, and guanidines were introduced into the reaction.

The participation of β -keto acid esters and β -diketones is the most widespread modification of the cyclocondensation reaction.

X = O, S; R = Ar, Alk

Cyclocondensation involving esters of β -keto acids and β -diketones

In this case, when R = Me, Et, Ph, OMe, OEt, the reaction has high yields even when it is carried out under standard conditions (HCl/EtOH) and requires special conditions only in the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents in the aldehyde component or when thioureas participate in the reaction. In addition

to condensation products with arylaldehydes, products based on heterocyclic aldehydes were obtained (the best yield for 2-thiophencarbaldehyde was 52%, the lowest yield for 8-quinolinecarbaldehyde was 28.6%) [7]:

For the reaction with aliphatic aldehydes, cyclocondensation products were obtained with significantly lower yields than for aryl and heterylaldehydes [8]:

For this reason, modified methods were developed. Two modifications of the cyclocondensation reaction are widespread: using "hidden carbonyl equivalents" and Etwell's modification [9].

The idea of using substances in the reaction, which in the reaction medium would give an aldehyde, which later participates in condensation, was implemented in the work [43, 44], where 2-substituted 1,3-oxazinans were used:

To introduce guanidines into the reaction, as well as to obtain O- or S-alkylated 1,4-dihydropyrimidines, it is convenient to use the modification proposed by Etwell [9]. In this method, the previously obtained benzylidene- β -ketoester adds guanidine according to Michael, followed by cyclization to 1,4-dihydropyrimidine.

It is proposed to use the method for electron-deficient aldehydes, cyclohexylcarbaldehyde and some others.

Instead of HCl, acetic or p-toluenesulfonic acid is used as a catalyst [10]. The best results were obtained in the presence of boron trifluoride [45], polyphosphoric ether [11], lanthanide compounds LaCl_3 [12],

Yb(OTf)₃ [13], lithium bromide [14], under conditions of microwave irradiation [15] and the so-called "solvent-free" reaction conditions (using a mixture of acidic or basic Yb(III)-modified polymers and a solid acid catalyst [16]) in the presence of ionic liquids, such as 1-n-butyl-3-methylimidazole tetrafluoroborate or its hexafluorophosphate [17].

Choosing an effective catalyst allows you to significantly increase yields. So, for example, for 2-bromo-4-nitrobenzaldehyde, the yield according to the standard method is close to 20%. The use of ytterbium triflate allows to increase it to 52% [13]. The work [18] reported on the synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid amide by nitrile hydrolysis:

But already in [19.] examples of syntheses with amides of β -keto acids as methylene carbonyl components are given:

X = O, S; R = Me, pyrrolidine, morpholine

The yields of acid derivatives are quite high.

The synthesis and physiological activity of tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxamides were studied in [20].

The possibility of using α -arylcarbonyl compounds in cyclocondensations was shown in an early work [21] using the example of acetophenone and phenylacetaldehyde:

R = H, CH₃

Variation of aromatic substituents logically led to the use of α -heteroaryl carbonyl compounds as methylene carbonyl components. Thus, in [22] the reaction of 2-phenacylbenzothiazole with aldehydes and urea (thiourea) was studied:

A = NH, NMe, S; X = S, O

Under the conditions of catalysis by alcoholic HCl, a mixture of products was obtained, which could not be separated. After optimizing the reaction conditions, the solvent, temperature, and ratio of reagents were selected. Cyclocondensation was carried out in acetic acid at 50°C. The molar ratio of aldehyde, phenacylbenzothiazole, and urea was 1:1.1:3. In this way, a yield of 72-97% was achieved.

The resulting cyclocondensation products are subjected to further functionalization. Thus, in [23], a con-

venient method for the synthesis of N(3)-ethoxycarbonyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-(1H)-2-one was developed, which consists in its acylation with a mixture of thionyl chloride and carboxylic acid.

In the thionyl chloride-carboxylic acid system (1:1 mol.), sufficient solubility of the starting compound is achieved due to an excess of acid. The optimal ratio for acylation of the starting substance, acid and thionyl chloride is 1:10:10 (mol). Under these conditions, it was possible to obtain N(3)-acyl derivatives with yields of 47-70%.

Another example of successful N-acylation is the synthesis of 3-(2-chloroacetyl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-4-phenyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate by the

action of chloroacetic anhydride on 3,4 -tetrahydropyrimidin-2-one. When interacting with thiourea in ethanol, an S-substituted derivative of isothiurea is formed:

The use of functionalized acetophenones [21]:

A = NO₂, Cl, OMe, OPh, SPh, NHC(O)CH₃

In [24, 25] it was proposed to use nitroacetone. The reaction was carried out under standard conditions (HCl/EtOH). The product was obtained with a yield of 91%:

R = CH₃, Ph; X = O, S

A significant expansion of the spectrum of methylene components and the selection of new reaction conditions led to improved yields for low-activity aldehydes. At the same time, the circle of ureas is practically limited only to unsubstituted urea and thiourea. In

But a similar reaction (with the formation of arylmethanediureides) also occurs in one of the stages of the Biginelli reaction. It was shown in [27] that the TMSCl-DMF system allows the process to be carried out at room temperature and to obtain the target products with yields of 62-80% with aromatic aldehydes and 32-37% with aliphatic ones. The reaction was carried out in two stages: urea was added to the reaction mixture after the completion of the croton condensation of β -dicarbonyl compounds with aldehydes in the presence of TMSCl-DMF and the formation of unsaturated ketones.

this context, the work [26] is interesting, which discussed the use of the Me_3SiCl -DMF system for the condensation of amides with carbonyl compounds. For example, when benzamide reacts with benzaldehyde, dicarboxamide is formed:

In work [28] it was shown that high yields of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones (76-97%) can be obtained using TMSCl in a mixture of MeCN-DMF (2:1) based on various aromatic, aliphatic and α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, ureas and thioureas, acetylacetone and acetoacetic ester.

Cycloalkanones can be used instead of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds in cyclocondensation [29]. When cyclic ketones interact with urea or thiourea and aromatic aldehydes in the TMSCl/MeCN/DMF system, depending on their ratio, the formation of three types of products is possible:

condensed heterocyclic (A), benzylidene heterobicyclic (B) and spiroheterotricyclic (C) pyrimidines:

For example, as a result of the reaction of cyclopentanone with urea and aromatic aldehydes, which do not contain an electron-withdrawing group in the para

position, in the presence of TMSCl/MeCN/DMF at room temperature, benzylidene heterobicyclic pyrimidines (B) are formed with yields of 78-95%:

p-Fluorobenzaldehyde under similar conditions gives a mixture of products (B) and (C) in the ratio 87:13.

Aliphatic aldehydes are less reactive than aromatic aldehydes and give good yields of condensation products only when boiling. Cycloalkanones with a ring size

For example, during the interaction of cyclooctanone and cyclodecanone with aliphatic aldehydes and thiourea, condensed heterobicyclic pyrimidines (A) are formed with yields of 70-85%.

greater than 7 react with ureas or thioureas and aliphatic aldehydes to form spirocondensed heterotricyclic compounds (C) or condensed heterobicyclics (A):

Condensation reactions of butyric and valeric aldehydes with urea under the influence of TMSCl in a mixture of DMF/MeCN lead to the formation of 5,6-dihydro-(1H)-pyrimidin-2-ones (D) with yields of 53% and 62%, respectively:

a; R = $n\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5$ (53%)
b; R = $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$ (62%)

During the interaction of isovaleric aldehyde with urea or thiourea under similar conditions, 3,4-dihydro-(1H)-pyrimidin-2-ones (E) are formed, cyclohexanone with urea gives a spiroheterocyclic product (F) with a yield of 78%:

Condensation of 1,3-cyclohexanedione with urea or thiourea in the presence of TMSCl as a Lewis acid in a mixture of DMF/MeCN (1:2) leads to the formation of the corresponding heterobicyclic (G) and spirocondensed (H) compounds in high yields [30]:

At the same time, benzaldehyde and para-substituted aromatic aldehydes give a mixture of two compounds with a predominant content of the spiro product, while ortho- and meta-substituted aromatic aldehydes and aliphatic aldehydes react under similar conditions with the selective formation of octahydroquinazolinones.

Similarly, a series of octahydroquinazolinones (H) was obtained as a result of a one-step three-component condensation starting from dimedone, of aromatic aldehydes and ureas in the presence of TMSCl when boiling in a mixture of MeCN/DMF (1:4) [31].

Other silicon derivatives can be used as condensing agents in the reaction. So TMSI, generated from TMSCl and NaI, was successfully used for the cycliza-

tion of aromatic, aliphatic, heterocyclic, and α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, ureas, and a β -dicarbonyl compound (acetylacetone or acetoacetic ester) into dihydropyrimidin-2-(1H)-ones [28].

As it turned out, TMSOTf is an effective catalyst for the condensation reaction and leads to the formation of the corresponding products with yields of 80-95% [32].

Tetrahydropyrimidines (THP) have a wide spectrum of physiological activity. In the 1930s, their simplest representatives, for example (2a), were patented as insecticides [33]. Later, the effective antiviral drug nitracin (3a) was discovered [34]. Tetrahydropyrimidines manifest themselves as antitumor agents [35, 36].

Compounds of type (4a) have antipyretic properties and are anticoagulants [37].

However, THPs are most interesting as antihypertensive agents, for example, analogues of nifedipine

(6a) and (7a) [38, 39]. Particularly active in this area are the disubstituted by the provision of N-3: (8a) and (9a) [40].

The ability of dihydropyrimidines to block calcium ion channels is described. 1,4-Dihydropyrimidines (nifedipine, nitrendipine, nimodipine, amlodipine, lacidipine, felodipine, nicardipine, isradipine, etc.) are antagonists of L-type calcium antagonists.

The action of these drugs is focused on lowering blood pressure. Due to this, some of them act as sedatives and are medicines for optic nerve dysfunction.

Known derivatives of the 4-oxopyrimidine series containing heterocyclic substituents, namely: imidazole, pyridine, thiazole, which have antihistaminic activity.

Derivatives of 4(3H)-pyrimidines have a tranquilizing effect. Oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidine salts have antidepressant and tranquilizing effects.

The synthesis of oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidine derivatives, which have immunotropic activity, is described [41,42].

The conducted studies show that the described compounds have a pronounced antihistamine effect, which is two or more times greater than the activity of diazolin, while being practically non-toxic.

The purpose of this work was to obtain and study the products of the heterocyclization reaction using trimethylhalosilanes and CF_3 - β -diketones, to study the effect of substituents on the reaction direction of the latter, and to optimize the synthesis method.

Materials and methods.

Chromatograms and LC/MS spectra were obtained on an "Agilent 1100 Series" instrument equipped with an "Agilent LC/MSD SL" detector.

^1H NMR spectra (400 MHz and 500 MHz) were recorded on Varian Mercury-400 and Bruker Avance DRX 500 NMR spectrometers with TMS as an internal standard.

All reagents were obtained from commercially available sources (Aldrich, Fluka) and were used without further purification. DMF was freshly distilled and dried by a standard method. Control of the amount of water in the solvents ($<0.05\%$) was performed by the Fisher method using a Mettler Toledo DL31 KF Titrator. Melting points were measured on a Buchi apparatus. Before determining the melting temperature, performing elemental analysis and spectral studies, all product samples were dried for 3-5 hours in a vacuum of 12-15 mm. at 80-100°C.

General method of synthesis of derivatives of tetrahydropyrimidinones and tetrahydropyrimidinethiones from unsubstituted ureas and thioureas.

To a solution of 0.022 mmol of urea or thiourea in 20 ml of DMF, add 0.01 mmol of aldehyde and 0.01

mmol of diketone and stir until dissolved. Then add 15 ml (~ 0.12 mmol) of Me_3SiCl and quickly cover with a stopper. The flask with the reaction mixture is left for 48 hours at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (a sign is the delamination of the reaction mass), the reaction mass is poured with stirring into 50-60 ml of ice water. The deposited precipitate is filtered, washed with water and 2-3 times with methanol in portions of 10 ml. The filtered sediment is dried in air. Recrystallized from methanol. The yields of target products are 80-86%.

General method of synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidinone and tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivatives from monosubstituted ureas and thioureas.

To a solution of 0.022 mmol of urea or thiourea in 20 ml of DMF, add 0.01 mmol of aldehyde and 0.01 mmol of diketone and stir until dissolved. Then 15 ml (~ 0.12 mmol) of Me_3SiCl is added and immediately closed with a cap. The reactor with the reaction mixture is left for 4 days at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (a sign is the delamination of the reaction mass), the reaction mass is poured with stirring into 50-60 ml of ice water. The deposited precipitate is filtered, washed with water and 2-3 times with methanol in portions of 10 ml. The filtered sediment is dried in air. Recrystallized from methanol. The yields of target products are 82-90%.

General method of synthesis of tetrahydropyrimidinone and tetrahydropyrimidinethione derivatives from disubstituted ureas and thioureas.

To a solution of 0.022 mmol of urea (thiourea) in 20 ml of DMF, add 0.010 mmol of aldehyde and 0.010 mmol of diketone and stir until dissolved. Then 15 ml

(~0.12 mmol) of Me_3SiCl is added and quickly closed with a cap. Leave for 3 days at room temperature. After completion of the reaction (a sign is the delamination of the reaction mass), the reaction mass is poured with stirring into 50-60 ml of ice water. The deposited precipitate is filtered, washed with water and 2-3 times

with methanol in portions of 10 ml. The filtered sediment is dried in air. Recrystallized from ethanol. The yields of target products are 78-83%.

Discussion of results.

In the synthesis, halosilanes with such halogens as chlorine, bromine, and iodine were used. Me_3SiI was synthesized in situ from Me_3SiCl and NaI in DMF.

Cyclocondensation reaction using halosilanes

Me_3SiCl has previously been shown to be an effective promoter and dewatering agent in various condensations. It was decided to try it as a condensing reagent and in cyclocondensation reactions with various substituted ureas and thioureas. Benzaldehyde, acetoethyl acetate, phenylurea and phenylthiourea were used to develop the technique. By varying the solvent, ratio of reagents, temperature and reaction time, 100% conversion was achieved for the model compounds. The use of Me_3SiBr and Me_3SiI does not give any advantage over Me_3SiCl . The optimal conditions for the

reaction were: reaction temperature 20°C, dimethylformamide solvent, reaction time 48 hours, presence of 4 equivalents of Me_3SiCl .

The use of Me_3SiCl made it possible to introduce a wide range of aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes, mono- and disubstituted ureas and thioureas into the reaction. It was also possible to use spatially hindered ureas and thioureas, aromatic aldehydes with donor and acceptor substituents in the 2 and 6 positions. At the same time, alkylaryl and diarylureas and thioureas turned out to be unreactive.

¹H NMR data (DMSO-*d*₆, 400 MHz) for 3,4-dihydropyrimidine-2(1H)-thiones

β -Diketones take part in cyclocondensation reactions as bifunctional reagents. At the same time, there is no information on the participation of CF_3 - β -diketones in such reactions in the literature, although the presence of a pharmacophore fluorine atom could

give the reaction products new physiologically active properties.

The DMF/TMSCl system was used. CF_3 - β -diketones (7a-d), ureas and thioureas (8a-h), and benzaldehyde (9) were selected as model compounds:

(7 a-d)

7a: R = CF₃

7b: R = OEt

7c: R = Ph

7d: R = Me

(8 a-h)

8a: X = O, R₁ = R₂ = H8b: X = O, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me8c: X = O, R₁ = R₂ = Me8d: X = O, R₁ = H, R₂ = *p*-Tol

(9)

8e: X = S, R₁ = R₂ = H8f: X = S, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me8g: X = S, R₁ = R₂ = Me8h: X = S, R₁ = H, R₂ = Ph

Optimized conditions were used for the reaction:

First, unsubstituted ureas and thioureas (8a, 8e) were introduced into the reaction. as a result, hydroxy derivatives (10) were isolated.

When transitioning to substituted ureas and thioureas, a very interesting dependence of the behavior of the diketone (7a-d) on the nature of the R substituents was observed.

In the case of R= Ph, OEt, CF₃ (7a-e), the formation of compounds of type (11) was observed. However, when going to R = Me (7d), the regioselectivity was reversed with the formation of cyclization products (12) on the other carbonyl group.

R = CF₃, OEt, Ph, MeX = O, S; R₁ = H, Me; R₂ = Me, Ph

Behavior of CF₃-β-diketones in the heterocyclization reaction

Conclusions.

As a result of the work carried out, a method for using trimethylchlorosilane for the cyclocondensation reactions of substituted ureas and thioureas was developed and optimized. It was possible to achieve quantitative yields of the target products.

For the first time, CF₃-β-diketones were introduced into the cyclocondensation reaction, which, due to the presence of the pharmacoformal CF₃ group, can be potentially physiologically active substrates.

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